

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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NOTE - 003

Report of I.FAST Workshop on Stability of Storage Ring Based Light Sources

WP 7 Task 7.2

ABSTRACT

The I.FAST workshop on the stability of storage ring-based light sources, organized by SOLEIL and KIT, took place from March 17th to 21st, 2025. The workshop took place at KIT campus north and featured 26 scientific presentations from institutes and universities in Europe, the Americas, and the Asia-Pacific region. The workshop was a great success in networking the accelerator community, especially between the fields of beam dynamics and hardware. This document summarizes the workshop's objectives and scientific program, including the abstracts. The presentations are published on the following Indico website: <https://indico.kit.edu/event/4809/>.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. Introduction

For future synchrotron light sources with ultra-low emittance beams, light source stability is paramount to exploiting the properties of high-quality beams. Beam stability issues have been identified as a relevant topic in synchrotron light sources, considering both the hardware and the beam dynamics from a time range of sub-microseconds to years. The goal of the workshop was to share the latest information and knowledge on beam dynamics to improve understanding of and methods to ensure stable beam operation and relevant hardware.

The workshop was organized by a joint organization of Synchrotron SOLEIL in France and the Institute for Beam Physics and Technology (IBPT) at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). The 1.5-day scientific program was held in a hybrid style to consider speakers and audience members who could not attend the workshop in person. As a result, the workshop featured 26 scientific presentations and had 86 registered participants (52 on-site and 34 online) from Europe, the Americas, and the Asia-Pacific region from different research and industrial areas.

Immediately after the workshop, the workshop participants joined a joint experiment at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA) to conduct experiments regarding beam stabilities. This experiment was organized as part of the EURO-LABS project, and most workshop participants joined the experiment that followed the workshop.

Below, we have provided a summary of the workshop, including the program, list of presentations, list of participants, and abstracts of the scientific presentations.

2. Workshop Contents

2.1 SCIENTIFIC SESSION CATEGORIES

To provide opportunities for sharing information and knowledge and networking with different research fields, the stability workshop had the following five scientific session categories covering a wide range of stability issues on storage-ring-based light sources.

- Source position stability
 - Beam dynamics, beam orbit feedback system, beam position stability, beam position monitoring and diagnostics, transparent beam injection, AI-based beam orbit correction
- Resistive and permanent magnets
 - Magnetic field measurement and qualification strategies, magnet and girder system design, radiation damage issues in permanent magnet systems, development of permanent magnet systems
- Infrastructure
 - Analysis of mechanical vibrations on girders, beam-based girder alignment, stability of accelerator buildings and floors, girder design establishment
- Challenging issues
 - Beam diagnostics under extreme conditions, beam loss issues, new approaches to stabilising beams
- Orientation session for the joint experiment
 - Introduction to beam based alignment

2.2 WORKSHOP PROGRAM

Day 1 (17 March 2025)

The kick-off meeting took place at the Quadro City Hotel in Karlsruhe from 6:30 to 9:00 p.m. During the meeting, the workshop organizer gave an introductory talk explaining the scientific background and past workshops regarding light source stability. Most workshop participants attended the meeting and learned about the history and aims of the workshop. After the talk, participants had time to share the latest information and network with each other in a casual atmosphere.

Day 2 (18 March 2025)

The scientific program started on the second day of the workshop at the large seminar room in building 348 (the KARA hall) on the KIT campus north. For speakers and audience who could not come to the workshop venue, all scientific presentations were conducted in a hybrid style. The following table shows the scientific program, including presentation titles, speakers' and session chairs' names. Discussion sessions for each session block took place after each presentation.

Session block	Presentation title	Speaker	Chair
Introduction	Welcome greetings and general information	A. Mochihashi (KIT)	
Source position stability: Part 1	SLS 2.0 BPM and Beam Feedback Systems - First Beam Commissioning Experience	B. Keil (PSI)	A. Mochihashi (KIT)
	Status of the design and simulations for the FOFB of PETRA IV	S. Pfeiffer (DESY)	
Source position stability: Part 2	The orbit stability issue in the initial commissioning stage of High Energy Photon Source	X. Huang (HEP)	I. Martin (DLS)
	Orbit Stability at BESSY II: Progress of FOFB Upgrade and Current Stability	G. Rehm (HZB)	
	Application of deep learning method for insertion device orbit and coupling feedforward at the SSRF	X. Liu (SSRF)	
Source position stability: Part 3	Orbit stability and reproducibility at SOLARIS storage ring	A. Wawrzyniak (SOLARIS)	S. Pfeiffer (DESY)
	Design and commissioning of the asymmetric beam optics in the SSRF storage ring	S. Tian (SSRF)	
	BESSY III orbit correction scheme layout and performance	S. Joly (HZB)	
Source position stability: Part 4	A transparent injection scheme for Diamond-II	I. Martin (DLS)	X. Huang (IHEP)
	Experimental Application of Neural Network Fast Feedback Modeling at the Canadian Light Source	S. Saadat (CLS)	
	Silicon Carbide based X ray beam monitoring	M. Camarda (SenSic, STLab)	
Resistive and permanent magnets: Part 1	Qualification of Series Magnets in the SLS Upgrade at the Paul Scherrer Institute: Challenges, Results, and Lessons Learned	S. Sanfilippo (PSI)	C. Benabderrahmane (ESRF)
	Elettra 2.0 magnets and girders	D. Castronovo (Elettra)	

Day 3 (19 March 2025)

Scientific presentations also took place on the third day of the workshop. A special session was organised to discuss plans for the joint experiment that followed the workshop. During the orientation session for the joint experiment, a speaker presented the basic concepts of beam-based alignment, aiming to clarify the experimental topics.

Session block	Presentation title	Speaker	Chair
Additional session	HEPS Fast Orbit Feedback System	S. Wei (IHEP)	A. Mochihashi (KIT)
Resistive and permanent magnets: Part 2	Radiation damage in permanent magnet materials	B. Shepherd (ASTeC)	S. Fatehi (KIT)
	Development of permanent magnet dipoles for ESRF-EBS	C. Benabderrahmane (ESRF)	
Orientation session for the joint experiment	Orientation talk for joint experiment: Quadrupole offset measurement by BBA	C. Goffing (KIT, CERN)	A.Mochihashi (KIT)
	Introduction of KARA storage ring	A. Mochihashi (KIT)	
Infrastructure: Part 1	Vibration analysis and stability control for High Energy Photon Source in China	F. Yan (IHEP)	G. Rehm (HZB)
	Beam-based girder alignment in PETRA-IV: conceptual simulations	S. Hussain Mirza (DESY)	
Infrastructure: Part 2	Effects of the ALBA slab movement on ALBA-II	O. Roberto Blanco García (ALBA)	J. Breunlin (MAX)
	Topology-Optimized Girder Design for PETRA IV: Achieving High Eigenfrequencies for Enhanced Stability	N. Koldrack (DESY)	
Challenging issues:Part 1	Statistical and interferometric beam diagnostics in IOTA at Fermilab	G. Stancari (Fermilab, UChicago)	A. Mochihashi (KIT)
	Beam position measurements: from pickups to stable beams	D. El Khechen (KIT)	
	Bunch-by-bunch feedback system used as a diagnostic device for multi-bunch instabilities in the DAΦNE collider	D. Quartullo (INFN)	

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Session block	Presentation title	Speaker	Chair
Challenging issues: Part 2	Observing sudden beam loss events using bunch-by-bunch BPMs at SuperKEKB	R. Nomaru (UTokyo, KEK)	D. El Khechen (KIT)
	Microbunching control and CSR stabilization at KIT-KARA	L. Scomparin (KIT)	
	Development of Control Systems for the Stabilization of Synchrotron X-Ray beams	N. La Rosa (UCatania)	

Day 4 and 5 (20-21 March 2025)

Following the workshop, a joint experiment was organised at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA) facility. This experiment was organised as part of the EURO-LABS project, of which KIT is a member. The experiment used the KARA 2.5 GeV electron storage ring and aimed to clarify the characteristics of the parallel beam-based alignment method, as well as considering the differences between this method and the individual (or normal) beam-based method. The participants discussed and shared the experimental plans beforehand, and the measurements were carried out systematically using real electron beams to obtain concrete, systematic data. Data analysis is ongoing, and the results are providing us with relevant information about the parallel beam-based alignment method.

2.3 ABSTRACTS

All speakers submitted abstracts, which were also made available on the workshop Indico website. The following section summarises the abstracts, alongside the presentation title and speaker information.

Session: Source position stability

SLS 2.0 BPM and Beam Feedback Systems - First Beam Commissioning Experience

Boris Keil (PSI)

After more than 20 years of successful operation, the storage ring of the Swiss Light Source SLS has been replaced with a new diffraction-limited ring called SLS 2.0, providing more than 40 times higher brilliance to hard X-ray experiments. The new ring was installed during a 15 month dark time from September 2023 until December 2024, with first stored beam in January 2025. This contribution will give an overview of the RF beam position monitor and beam based feedback systems of SLS 2.0, and the first beam commissioning experience.

Session: Source position stability

Status of the design and simulations for the FOFB of PETRA IV

Sven Pfeiffer, Sajjad H. Mirza, Holger Schlarb (DESY)

PETRA III is one of the most important facilities at DESY. The PETRA IV project aims to replace PETRA III with an ultra-low emittance ring (20 pm), add a new experimental hall in two additional octants and replace DESY II with a new low emittance booster. In this way, the emittance will be reduced from 1300 pm to 20 pm. A brief overview of the activities on the way to a stable beam orbit will be given. The following points will be introduced during the presentation: The stability task force, the system modelling and hardware design, the perturbation and noise models used and the SISO simulation as a first step towards a full ring simulation. Finally, we will conclude the presentation.

The orbit stability issue in the initial commissioning stage of High Energy Photon Source

Xiyang Huang (IHEP)

The High Energy Photon Source (HEPS), a fourth-generation light source with designed emittance of less than 60 pm, faces significant challenges in achieving orbit stability due to its small beam sizes. In this report, we'll briefly introduce HEPS's early-stage storage ring beam commissioning and the beam status. Also, we'll cover the orbit instability issues met during initial commissioning and relevant analysis.

Orbit Stability at BESSY II: Progress of FOFB Upgrade and Current Stability

Günther Rehm, Danielle Löhr, Pierre Schnitzer (HZB)

The Beam Position Monitor (BPM) System at BESSY II is currently in the process of an upgrade from analogue multiplexing BPMs with low frequency Analogue to Digital Converters (ADC) to modern fully integrated digital BPMs. At the same time, the Fast Orbit Feedback (FOFB) is being adapted and upgraded to enable un-interrupted operation during the 6 to 12 months upgrade period. With 3/16 of the upgrade complete, a review of the plan, challenges in implementation and future steps will be provided. Furthermore, recent challenges to orbit stability arising from more or lesser-known disturbances will be summarised.

Session: Source position stability

**Application of deep learning method for insertion device orbit and coupling feedforward
at the SSRF**

Xinzhong Liu (SSRF)

The Shanghai Synchrotron Radiation Facility (SSRF), a third-generation synchrotron radiation source, demands exceptional beam stability for high-precision user experiments. However, manufacturing and installation inaccuracies in insertion devices (IDs) can lead to beam orbit and coupling distortions. To address this, we developed a data-driven predictive model leveraging deep learning to forecast the effects of ID gap variations. The model facilitates real-time feedback control by adjusting corrector and skew quadrupole currents, effectively mitigating ID-induced perturbations on beam orbit and coupling. Implementation at SSRF demonstrates a substantial reduction in these perturbations, resulting in enhanced experimental stability and reliability.

Orbit stability and reproducibility at SOLARIS storage ring

Adriana Wawrzyniak (SOLARIS)

Ensuring the stability of the electron beam at the SOLARIS synchrotron has been a key objective throughout its development. Several structural measures, including the installation of a vibro-elastomer mat and concrete block magnet girders, have effectively maintained the stability of the experimental hall within acceptable limits below 1.6 μm rms for low frequency range (below 10Hz) and below 0.3 μm rms in the frequency range between 10 and 50Hz. Thermal stability, particularly in the cooling water system, has been progressively enhanced, culminating in a major upgrade in 2022 that achieved a stability level of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The orbit correction system has undergone significant improvements, with the Slow Orbit Feedback (SOFB) system being redesigned and accelerated by over an order of magnitude. Additionally, the successful development and implementation of the Fast Orbit Feedback (FOFB) system have further refined beam stability. To optimize performance, an offloading procedure was introduced, mitigating conflicts between the SOFB and FOFB systems. These advancements have enabled submicron precision in electron beam stability and reproducibility. While beam position reproducibility remains at a high level, the drifts of several micrometres over 12 h persist in the X-ray Beam Position Monitor (XBPM) readouts. Continuous efforts are being made to further enhance long-term orbit stability for the most demanding experimental applications.

Session: Source position stability

Design and commissioning of the asymmetric beam optics in the SSRF storage ring

Shunqiang TIAN (SSRF)

Lattice upgrade, consisting of replacing the conventional bending magnets with super-bend locally, constructing two double-mini- β y optics (DMB) and installing a superconducting wiggler (SCW), was implemented in the Beamline-Project of Shanghai Synchrotron Radiation Facility (SSRF). The symmetry of the SSRF storage ring was completely destroyed, forcing the global optics to be modified. The lattice of the new SSRF storage ring, matching the new elements perfectly, was designed. Sufficient dynamic aperture and energy acceptance were obtained by elaborate lattice design and nonlinear optimization. Study on beam dynamics, including the closed orbit correction, the linear optics correction, the coupling correction, the chromaticity correction and the nonlinear dynamic optimization, achieved good results for the new lattice. The critical step in the study is the restoration of the linear beam optics, which greatly restored the machine performance. The resulting beam parameters, as well as the operation status, are also presented.

BESSY III orbit correction scheme layout and performance

Sebastien Joly, Benat Alberdi Esuain, Paul Goslawski (HZB)

Currently in its Conceptual Design Phase (CDR), the 4th generation light source BESSY III aims to become a world-leading soft X-ray source, enabling numerous applications in metrology, life sciences, energy and catalysis materials, and many more. Its performance relies on ultra-low transverse emittances, achieved through the use of strong focusing magnetic elements that are sensitive to magnetic and alignment errors. If left uncorrected, these errors give rise to a distortion of the closed orbit, beta beating, linear coupling, and a stronger impact of resonances thus impairing the storage ring performance. In this work, we address how to devise an initial BESSY III orbit correction scheme. Two criteria were considered to find the optimal locations of Beam Position Monitor (BPM) and dipolar Corrector Magnet (CM). Different orbit correction scheme candidates are presented and their advantages and disadvantages are discussed. All calculations were performed in parallel with the Matlab toolkit Simulated Commissioning (SC) and its Python counterpart (pySC).

Session: Source position stability

A Transparent injection scheme for Diamond-II

Ian Martin (DLS)

This talk presents an overview of the injection schemes that have been developed for Diamond-II. Two complementary injection schemes will be used. The first scheme uses a standard four-kicker bump with permanent magnet main septum and pulsed thin septum magnet for commissioning of the new storage ring and fast filling in multi-bunch mode. The second scheme makes use of fast (3 ns) single-bunch stripline kickers for transparent injection during top-up. These striplines can be used either for aperture-sharing injection or kick-and-cancel injection. The principles behind these two schemes are described and the simulated performances are compared. The talk concludes by describing the hardware specifications of the injection magnets and status of prototyping.

Session: Source position stability (as an additional session)

Design and implementation of the HEPS FOFB system

*Shu-Jun Wei¹, Guo-Dong Gao¹, Hong Zhang², Yi-Lin Li^{1,2}, Dai-Quan Zhou^{1,2}, Xi-Yang Huang¹,
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The Fast Orbit Feedback System (FOFB) is a critical control system designed to enhance the beam orbit stability of the High Energy Photon Source (HEPS). This paper discusses the design of a "ring-star-ring" network topology specifically tailored to the requirements of the HEPS FOFB system. Based on this topology, the comprehensive design, mass production, installation, and testing have been successfully completed. Furthermore, the development of the FOFB algorithms and associated upper-level control application programs has been carried out. Finally, through collaborative laboratory testing and delay time measurements of all components, it has been confirmed that the overall response time of this FOFB system, under the current hardware version, meets the feedback bandwidth requirements for the HEPS project. We anticipate that the FOFB system will play a significant role in enhancing beam orbit stability at HEPS.

Session: Resistive and permanent magnets

**Qualification of Series Magnets in the SLS Upgrade at the Paul Scherrer Institute:
Challenges, Results, and Lessons Learned**

Stéphane Sanfilippo (PSI)

To enhance the performance of the Swiss Light Source (SLS) at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), a comprehensive upgrade known as SLS 2.0 is currently underway (2021–2026). This ambitious project involves the renewal of the storage ring, achieving 40 times lower emittance in user operation mode, thereby significantly increasing the source brightness, and enabling groundbreaking research capabilities. The SLS 2.0 upgrade imposes stringent requirements on field quality and magnetic alignment across a total of 1,285 magnets, which are being magnetically qualified at PSI. For the first time in a light source facility, the storage ring will utilize a unique combination of three magnet types: 1) NdFeB-based permanent magnets, offering high field quality with minimal power consumption. 2) Combined-function electromagnets, optimizing compactness and efficiency. 3) two 5-T Nb-Ti superconducting longitudinal gradient dipoles, to be installed during the second phase of the machine upgrade. This talk will provide an overview of the magnetic measurement challenges encountered during the project, the measurement strategy and results related to permanent and electromagnets, as well as the lessons learned from executing a large-scale magnetic test campaign achieving a 10⁻³ relative accuracy level under tight time constraints.

Radiation damage in permanent magnet materials

Ben Shepherd (ASTeC)

Rare earth permanent magnet (PM) devices, composed of either neodymium-iron-boron or samarium cobalt, are widely used in many accelerator facilities all over the world. One of the major concerns when assessing the suitability of PM-based magnets is their susceptibility to radiation. This talk will outline some of the experiments carried out over the years to understand how much radiation can be tolerated by PMs. There are multiple relevant variables, including PM material, grade and shape; demagnetising field; types and energies of particles; shielding materials and so on. Theoretical damage mechanisms are outlined, and mitigation strategies are described.

Session: Resistive and permanent magnets

Development of permanent magnet dipoles for ESRF-EBS

Chamseddine Benabderrahmane (ESRF)

The ESRF-EBS (Extremely Brilliant Source) is an upgrade done at ESRF (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility) in the period 2015-2022. It aims to decrease the horizontal emittance and to improve the brilliance and coherence of the X-ray beams to best serve the new science opportunities. Permanent magnet longitudinal dipoles (DLs) have been developed for the ESRF-EBS upgrade. The use of permanent magnets has mainly two advantages: on the one hand, it allows a more compact distribution of magnets, since there is no need of coils and water cooling; on the other hand, it allows to reduce the running costs and the carbon footprint of the facility thanks to the removal of the power supplies associated to conventional electromagnets. In this presentation I will report about the magnetic and mechanical design of these dipoles, prototype and series magnets production including thermal compensation, magnetic measurement and tuning. I will report also about the commissioning of this now machine and the problems related to the cross-talk between magnets. Finally, I will give feedback about the DLs after 5 years operation.

Session: Infrastructure

Vibration analysis and stability control for High Energy Photon Source in China

Fang Yan (IHEP)

The High Energy Photon Source (HEPS) is the first high-energy diffraction-limited storage ring (DLSR) light source built in China with designed natural emittance of 35 picometer radian. Beam stability is a critical issue for such an ultralow-emittance facility. To study ground vibration effects more closely aligned with reality, a novel beam dynamics analytical model is developed. In this model, different frequency influence together with wave speed caused phase difference and vibration decay are considered. The vibration controlling requirement are deduced using this model. The vibration specifications on storage ring floor is set to be 25nm for displacement RMS integral within frequency range of 1 to 100Hz. To control such rigorous restrictions, stable design concepts for the critical component such as slab, magnet and BPM girder are adopted to ensure the vibration not magnifying during propagation. The actual vibration control effect will be presented.

Session: Infrastructure

Beam-based girder alignment in PETRA-IV: conceptual simulations

Sajjad Hussain Mirza, Sven Pfeiffer (DESY)

DESY is advancing plans to upgrade PETRA III into a 4th generation light source. Magnetic lattice components are assembled and pre-aligned on extended girders before being installed in the tunnel. However, the considerable length of these girders and the inherent misalignment of the magnets introduce challenges for the PETRA IV lattice, particularly in storing the beam within the ring. Previous commissioning simulations indicated that the orbit correction system demands relatively high corrector strengths. In response, a simulation study was carried out to explore the feasibility of beam-based girder alignment correction as a means to reduce these corrector strength requirements during operation.

Effects of the ALBA slab movement on ALBA-II

Oscar Roberto Blanco Garcia (ALBA)

The Spanish 3rd generation synchrotron light source ALBA of 268.8 m and 3 GeV, is planning to renovate the Storage Ring to a 4th generation synchrotron, called ALBA-II, to be installed in the same location. The current ALBA storage ring has been used to validate the ALBA model behaviour subject to ground motion and the ALBA-II ground movement studies have been based on 6-months and 1-year cycles from 2022 and 2023 alignment data. The ground movement seems non-cumulative in the most recent years, large amplitude and low spatial frequency. The lattice could be corrected in case of either: a 6-months or 1-year of continuous motion modelled as low spatial frequency and high amplitude components that increase the orbit correction budget by less than 50 μrad and would be continuously used; or weeks/months of continuous motion modelled as girder to girder variations of 10 μrad rms cut at 2 sigma, equivalent to jumps of 40 μm , contributing to another 50 μrad to the corrector budget. Girder movers could help to reduce the corrector budget by removing the girder-to-girder jumps. In case of non-continuous correction we expect once every 5 years at most 1 mm loss in horizontal D.A. This is the case of a long stop, for example in winter or summer, and could reduce efficiency or stop off-axis injection. As a way to mitigate this issue we will keep the possibility to come back to on-axis injection, allowing to inject, diagnose, correct and recover fully the D.A. Alternatives to increase the D.A. from design so that we can tolerate 1 mm hor. DA. loss are also foreseen.

Session: Challenging issues

Statistical and interferometric beam diagnostics in IOTA at Fermilab

Giulio Stancari (Fermilab, The University of Chicago)

At the Fermilab Integrable Optics Test Accelerator (IOTA), we are carrying out a research program on the statistical and quantum-optical properties of undulator radiation from electron bunches down to single electrons [1]. As a result of this program, novel beam diagnostic techniques have been developed. From the intensity fluctuations of undulator radiation, it is possible to infer very small beam sizes, which would otherwise be very challenging to observe [2]. In addition, we applied interferometric methods to observe vibrations of the apparatus at the nanometer scale [3]. A review of these methods is given, with an outlook on possible developments.

[1] <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-MOPG06>

[2] <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.126.134802>

[3] <https://rpubs.com/gist/clara-vibration-studies> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14897587>

Beam position measurements: from pickups to stable beams

Dima El Khechen, Patrick Schreiber, Nigel Smale (KIT)

The KIT project, cSTART (Compact storage ring for accelerator research and technology), aims to demonstrate the injection and storage of the sub-ps bunches like and from a LPA (Laser plasma accelerator). The long damping time of the low energy beam (50 to 90 MeV) compared to the storage time grants opportunities to study non-equilibrium beam dynamics. With non-equilibrium beams, beam parameters like bunch charge, bunch length etc. are expected to change drastically over the turns especially in the very few turns after injection and thus this requires fast and precise beam diagnostics (turn-by-turn, 6.9 MHz). In this talk, we present the cSTART project and we elaborate on the beam position diagnostics system including the pickup electrodes and the turn-by-turn readout electronics. Furthermore, we present preliminary results of few characterisation tests on a readout prototype unit with signal generators. In addition, we show preliminary results on misalignment studies and orbit corrections using specified resolution of turn-by-turn beam position measurements.

Session: Challenging issues

Bunch-by-bunch feedback system used as a diagnostic device for multi-bunch instabilities in the DAΦNE collider

Danilo Quartullo (INFN)

DAΦNE is an electron-positron collider operating at INFN-LNF. Bunch-by-bunch feedback systems installed in each of the two rings allow to store high-intensity and stable beams, by counteracting strong coupled-bunch instabilities due to e-cloud and RF higher-order modes. These feedback systems can be also used as a diagnostic tool which is able to measure beam parameters which are important for the evaluation of the instabilities. In this talk, we first describe the acquisition system used to record the beam data obtained with the feedback systems. Then we report transverse-tune shift and grow-damp measurements performed in 2024 with positron beams, by using the feedback systems as a diagnostic device. These measurements contributed to the characterization of the e-cloud beam instability, which currently is one of the main limitations for the DAΦNE performances. Finally, we describe the first beam measurements and feedback-system setup designed to automatically record turn-by-turn bunch position displacements when an unexpected loss in beam current occurs due to any faults in the collider. This tool can be useful in identifying the causes of these events.

Observing sudden beam loss events using bunch-by-bunch BPMs at SuperKEKB

Riku Nomaru (KEK, The University of Tokyo)

SuperKEKB is an electron-positron collider aiming for high luminosity. However, its stable operation is challenged by Sudden Beam Loss (SBL), where beam instability occurs within tens of microseconds, leading to significant beam loss and triggering a beam abort. To better understand and mitigate SBL, we developed a new Bunch Oscillation Recorder (BOR) using AMD/Xilinx RFSoc. The BOR records bunch-by-bunch beam position and charge before a beam abort. In the 2024 operation, two BORs were deployed in the main ring, enabling detailed observation of SBL. Analysis of the BOR data revealed that during SBL, not only do bunch positions oscillate, but their sizes also increase. Furthermore, SBL is strongly correlated with "pressure burst", where the local vacuum pressure in the beam chamber rises abnormally at specific locations. Our results suggest that at these locations, the beam may receive kicks, triggering instability. Inspections of these locations revealed dust and vacuum seal contamination in the chamber, suggesting that interactions between the beam and these foreign materials could be a potential cause of SBL.

3. Participants List

ONSITE PARTICIPANTS REGISTERED

No.	First Name	Last Name	Affiliation
1	Shohan	Banerjee	Diamond Light Source
2	Chamseddine	Benabderrahmane	ESRF European Synchrotron
3	Oscar Roberto	Blanco Garcia	ALBA CELLS
4	Edmund	Blomley	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
5	Jonas	Breunlin	MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University
6	Davide	Castronovo	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste
7	Dima	El Khechen	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
8	Samira	Fatehi	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
9	Ferran	Fernandez	ALBA-CELLS Synchrotron
10	Christian	Goffing	CERN and KIT
11	Xiyang	Huang	Institute of High Energy Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences
12	Nicolas	HUBERT	Synchrotron SOLEIL
13	Sebastien	Joly	HZB
14	Boris	Keil	Paul Scherrer Institut
15	Normann	Koldrack	DESY
16	Peter	Leban	Instrumentation Technologies d.o.o
17	Anton	Malygin	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
18	Koryun	Manukyan	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste
19	Ian	Martin	Diamond Light Source
20	Akira	Mochihashi	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
21	Anke-Susanne	Müller	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
22	Marvin	Noll	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
23	Riku	Nomaru	The University of Tokyo
24	Sven	Pfeiffer	DESY
25	Danilo	Quartullo	INFN-LNF
26	Christoph	Quitmann	RI Research Instruments
27	Günther	Rehm	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin

28	Robert	Ruprecht	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
29	Shervin	Saadat	Accelerator Physicist at Canadian Light Source Inc.
30	Stephane	Sanfilippo	Paul Scherrer Institut
31	Volker	Schlott	Paul Scherrer Institut
32	Patrick	Schreiber	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
33	Marcel	Schuh	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
34	Luca	Scomparin	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
35	Ben	Shepherd	STFC Daresbury Laboratory
36	Giulio	Stancari	Fermilab / The University of Chicago
37	Shujun	Wei	Institute of High Energy Physics, CAS
38	Chenran	Xu	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
39	Haisheng	Xu	Institute of High Energy Physics
40	Siti Hajar	Zuber	The National University of Malaysia

Plus 11 participants whose names were not disclosed.

ON-LINE PARTICIPANTS REGISTERED

No.	First Name	Last Name	Affiliation
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19	Lu	ZHAO	Synchrotron SOLEIL
20	Dajun	Zhu	Australian Synchrotron
21	Mikhail	Zobov	INFN LNF

Plus 15 participants whose names were not disclosed.

4. References

All presentation slides which have been published and officially opened are available in the following Indico website. Additional information concerning the workshop is also available in the Indico website.

<https://indico.kit.edu/event/4809/>